

Acid Hydrazone Complexes of Niobium(v) and Tantalum(v) Ethoxides

A. K. NARULA

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 10 September 1990, revised 22 February 1991, accepted 27 May 1991

Reactions of niobium(v) and tantalum(v) ethoxides with salicylic acid hydrazone and anthranilic acid hydrazone in different stoichiometric ratios in refluxing benzene gave complexes of the types $[M(OEt)_{5-2n}(Sa)_n]$ and $[M(OEt)_{5-n}(Aa)_n]$, where, $M=Nb$ or Ta ; $n=1, 2$ or $1-3$. The corresponding t-butoxide derivatives $[M(OBu^t)_{5-2n}(Sa)_n]$ and $[M(OBu^t)_{5-n}(Aa)_n]$ were isolated by alcohol interchange reactions. The complexes have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral studies.

A large number of transition metal complexes of a variety of acid hydrazides and the corresponding hydrazones have been synthesised¹. However, no attempt has been made to synthesise niobium(v) and tantalum(v) complexes of acid hydrazides. Hence, it was considered worthwhile to study the reactions of ethoxides of niobium(v) and tantalum(v) with salicylic acid hydrazone (SaH_2) and anthranilic acid hydrazone (AaH).

Experimental

Niobium and tantalum pentaethoxides were prepared by standard method². Salicylic acid hydrazone and anthranilic acid hydrazone were prepared³ and recrystallised from hot water and chloroform, respectively.

The ir spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer. Ethanol was estimated by oxidimetric method⁴ using $1N K_2Cr_2O_7$ in 12.5% sulphuric acid. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Niobium and tantalum were estimated as Nb_2O_5 and Ta_2O_5 by direct ignition of compound after digestion with ammonia and nitric acid.

Reaction of niobium pentaethoxide with salicylic acid hydrazone (SaH_2): Niobium pentaethoxide (2.19 mmol) was refluxed with salicylic acid hydrazone (2.19 mmol) in dry benzene (~50 ml) for 6 h and the liberated ethanol was collected azeotropically and estimated⁵. The excess of solvent was then distilled off and the final product was dried under reduced pressure (40°/0.5 mm) when a red

solid was obtained (Found: EtOH in azeotrope, 0.20 g; Nb, 25.00; N, 70. Calcd. for $Nb(OEt)_5(Sa)$, 0.20 g; Nb, 24.5; N, 7.4%).

For the sake of brevity, other reactions are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of ethoxides of niobium(v) and tantalum(v) with salicylic acid hydrazone and anthranilic acid hydrazone in dry benzene has been carried out in different stoichiometric ratios,

where, $M=Nb$ or Ta . All the complexes are red to brown solids soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide, dimethyl formamide and non-volatile. They tend to decompose when heated under reduced pressure. Molecular weight could not be determined because of their insolubility in most of the organic solvents.

In case of salicylic acid hydrazone, the reaction proceeds with the removal of four moles of ethanol while in case of anthranilic acid hydrazone, with the removal of three moles of ethanol. It was observed that further removal of ethoxy group was very difficult even when excess ligand was taken and refluxing time increased. This might be ascribed to steric hindrance or saturated coordination state of metal in di/tri-substituted derivatives.

The infrared spectra of these ligands and related compounds and of their complexes have been discussed earlier⁶. In the salicylic acid hydrazone and anthranilic acid hydrazone complexes of niobium(v) and tantalum(v), the amide bands disappear on complexation and instead a strong band is observed at 1615–1610 cm^{-1} . This band has its origin in ν_{C-N} vibrations due to enolisation of keto group and amide group take part in bonding

TABLE 1—REACTIONS OF ETHOXIDES OF NbV AND TaV WITH SALICYLIC ACID HYDRAZIDE AND ANTHRANILIC ACID HYDRAZIDE*

Reactants		Reflux time h	Product	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
Alkoxide (mmol)	Ligand (mmol)				Amount of ethanol in azeotrope (g)	Metal	C	H	N
Nb(OEt) ₅ (2.19)	SaH ₂ (2.19)	6	[Nb(OEt) ₃ (Sa)]	Red	0.20 (0.20)	25.0 (24.5)	41.0 (41.3)	5.3 (5.6)	7.0 (7.4)
Nb(OEt) ₅ (3.68)	SaH ₂ (7.36)	9	[Nb(OEt)(Sa) ₂]	Red	0.65 (0.60)	21.5 (21.1)	43.4 (43.8)	3.6 (3.9)	12.0 (12.7)
Nb(OEt) ₅ (2.51)	AaH (2.51)	4	[Nb(OEt) ₄ (Aa)]	Brown	0.11 (0.11)	22.1 (21.9)	42.0 (42.6)	6.3 (6.7)	9.1 (9.9)
Nb(OEt) ₅ (2.90)	AaH (5.80)	7	[Nb(OEt) ₃ (Aa) ₂]	Brown	0.25 (0.26)	18.0 (17.5)	45.0 (45.5)	5.3 (5.9)	15.0 (15.9)
Nb(OEt) ₅ (2.92)	AaH (8.78)	10	[Nb(OEt) ₂ (Aa) ₃]	Brown	0.39 (0.40)	15.0 (14.6)	47.1 (47.4)	5.1 (5.4)	(19.8)
Ta(OEt) ₅ (1.87)	SaH ₂ (1.87)	6	[Ta(OEt) ₃ (Sa)]	Red	0.17 (0.17)	38.2 (38.8)	33.6 (33.5)	4.0 (4.5)	5.4 (6.0)
Ta(OEt) ₅ (1.13)	SaH ₂ (2.27)	10	[Ta(OEt)(Sa) ₂]	Brown	0.20 (0.21)	34.0 (34.3)	35.9 (36.5)	3.0 (3.3)	9.8 (10.6)
Ta(OEt) ₅ (1.59)	AaH (1.59)	5	[Ta(OEt) ₄ (Aa)]	Brown	0.07 (0.07)	35.0 (35.4)	34.7 (35.2)	5.6 (5.5)	7.3 (8.2)
Ta(OEt) ₅ (1.72)	AaH (3.45)	7	[Ta(OEt) ₃ (Aa) ₂]	Brown	0.16 (0.16)	29.0 (29.4)	38.3 (38.9)	4.6 (5.0)	12.5 (13.6)
Ta(OEt) ₅ (0.99)	AaH (2.97)	10	[Ta(OEt) ₂ (Aa) ₃]	Brown	0.13 (0.13)	24.4 (25.0)	41.2 (41.6)	4.4 (4.7)	18.6 (17.4)

*Yield=90-95% : SaH₂=salicylic acid hydrazide, AaH=Anthranilic acid hydrazide.

TABLE 2—INTERCHANGE REACTIONS OF [M(OEt)_{5-n}(Sa)_n] AND [M(OEt)_{5-n}(Aa)_n] WITH EXCESS OF t-BUTANOL

Alkoxide (mmol)	Reflux time h	Product	Colour	Metal % : Found/(Calcd.)
[Nb(OEt) ₅ (Sa)] (1.06)	4	[Nb(OBu ^t) ₅ (Sa)]	Red	21.0 (20.1)
[Nb(OEt)(Sa) ₂] (1.36)	4	[Nb(OBu ^t)(Sa) ₂]	Red	20.4 (19.9)
[Nb(OEt) ₄ (Aa)] (1.18)	5	[Nb(OBu ^t) ₄ (Aa)]	Brown	17.7 (17.3)
[Nb(OEt) ₃ (Aa) ₂] (1.25)	4	[Nb(OBu ^t) ₃ (Aa) ₂]	Brown	15.0 (15.1)
[Nb(OEt) ₂ (Aa) ₃] (0.95)	4	[Nb(OBu ^t) ₂ (Aa) ₃]	Brown	13.9 (13.5)
[Ta(OEt) ₅ (Sa)] (0.73)	4	[Ta(OBu ^t) ₅ (Sa)]	Brown	32.2 (32.8)
[Ta(OEt)(Sa) ₂] (0.76)	4	[Ta(OBu ^t)(Sa) ₂]	Brown	31.8 (32.6)
[Ta(OEt) ₄ (Aa)] (0.62)	6	[Ta(OBu ^t)(Aa)]	Brown	28.2 (29.0)
[Ta(OEt) ₃ (Aa) ₂] (0.82)	5	[Ta(OBu ^t) ₃ (Aa) ₂]	Brown	25.0 (25.8)
[Ta(OEt) ₂ (Aa) ₃] (0.61)	4	[Ta(OBu ^t) ₂ (Aa) ₃]	Brown	23.0 (23.2)

*Yield=90-65% : Sa=salicylic acid anion, Aa=anthranilic acid anion.

with the metal atom through enolic oxygen of the amide group. The enolisation of amide group is supported by the appearance of a band in the region ~1580-1570 cm⁻¹ attributable to ν_{NCO} vibration. The involvement of enolic oxygen in SaH₂ and AaH complexes can be attributed to greater basicity of the ligand⁷.

Salicylic acid hydrazide complexes of niobium(v) and tantalum(v) ethoxide show the disappearance of ν_{OH} vibration indicating the bond formation between phenolic oxygen and metal through deprotonation⁸. The two other bands characteristic of phenolic group

ν_{C=O} and δ_{C-O} occurring at 1480 and 1250 cm⁻¹ indicate that phenolic oxygen atoms are not involved in polymerisation. The bands at 530-500 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{M-O} phenolic vibrations.

However, in the anthranilic acid hydrazide complexes of niobium(v) and tantalum(v) ethoxide, lowering of ν_{NH} vibration (50 cm⁻¹) and diminishing intensity or disappearance of δ_{NH} band occurring at 750 cm⁻¹ are observed. The weak bands occurring at 450-400 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{M-N} vibrations⁹. On account of poor solubility of ligands, the pmr spectra were taken in DMSO-d₆. Anthranilic acid hydrazide

complexes of niobium and tantalum show a signal at δ 4.0, assignable to deshielded C-NH₂ group. The signals due to NH and CONH at δ 4.35-4.42 disappear indicating deprotonation through secondary nitrogen atom. Further, the signals due to phenolic proton of salicylic acid hydrazide also disappears indicating deprotonation of OH group. In addition, signals observed at δ 1.1-1.3 (t) and 3.5-3.8 (q) are assigned to CH₃ and CH₂ protons of ethoxy group. A multiplet appearing at δ 7.3 has been assigned to phenyl ring proton.

Thus, it appears that salicylic acid hydrazide is dinegatively charged and anthranilic acid hydrazide is mononegatively charged bidentate chelating agents having coordination sites at phenolic and enolic and amino atoms respectively. On the basis of above studies, a polymeric structure can tentatively be assigned to these complexes.

References

1. K. K. NARANG and R. C. AGGARWAL, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 651; D. K. RASTOGI, S. K. DUA, V. B. RANA and S. K. SAHNI, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1979, **8**, 97.
2. D. C. BRADLEY, W. WARDLAW and A. WHITALEY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 726; D. C. BRADLEY, B. N. CHAKRAVARTI, A. K. CHATTERJEE and W. WARDLAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2381; D. C. BRADLEY, B. N. CHAKRAVARTI and W. WARDLAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 4439.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1962, p. 395.
4. D. C. BRADLEY, F. M. A. HALIM and W. WARDLAW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3459.
5. S. K. SAHNI, S. P. GUPTA, S. K. SANGAL and V. B. RANA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1098.
6. R. K. SHARMA, R. V. SINGH and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 378; D. K. RASTOGI, S. K. DUA and S. K. SAHNI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1983, **42**, 23; A. K. NARULA, B. SINGH, P. N. KAFOOR and R. N. KAFOOR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 1296.
7. L. SACCONNI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4503.
8. M. MONOYAMA, S. TAMOTA and K. YAMASAKI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **12**, 333.
9. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 4th. Ed., Wiley, New York, 1986.